

BlogBites: A Full-Stack Blog Platform Using the MERN Stack

Anandu Sankar A P

Department of Master of Computer Applications

Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education,

Krishnankoil - 626 126, Virudhunagar, Tamil Nadu, INDIA

ananduap74@gmail.com

This project, titled "BlogBites," involves the development of a dynamic blogging platform using the MERN stack, which consists of MongoDB, Express, React, and Node.js. The purpose of BlogBites is to provide a dedicated platform where users can create, share, and interact with blogs while enjoying a seamless and interactive user experience. The application enables users to create profiles, upload personal photos, customize their profiles, and share blog content with the community.

I. INTRODUCTION

The "BlogBites" platform, developed using the MERN stack (MongoDB, Express, React, and Node.js), is an advanced application aimed at providing a responsive and dynamic environment for blogging and social engagement. The choice of the MERN stack facilitates full-stack JavaScript development, allowing seamless integration between the front end (React) and back end (Node.js with Express), while MongoDB serves as a scalable NoSQL database optimized for handling the dynamic data flow of a social platform [1]. This project integrates modern technologies for user authentication and security, employing JSON Web Tokens (JWT) to protect sensitive data and ensure authorized access, a necessity for any web-based system dealing with personal user information [2].

Additionally, BlogBites utilizes Redux Toolkit to streamline state management, which is particularly critical in complex applications that rely on consistent user states, such as authentication and real-time updates [3]. For chat functionality, Socket.io enables real-time bidirectional communication, allowing users to engage in synchronous discussions, which enhances the user experience and social interactivity on the platform [4]. Tailwind CSS aids in maintaining a responsive design, ensuring cross-device compatibility, an essential feature in today's mobile-centric web environment [5]. Furthermore, RESTful API principles underlie the platform's structure, fostering a modular and reusable codebase that can be expanded with new services as needed [6]. The architecture and technology stack employed in this project not only meet the core requirements of a blogging platform but also demonstrate scalable, secure, and interactive design practices for modern web applications.

II. TECHNOLOGIES USED

MERN Stack Overview: The project leverages the MERN stack, a powerful and widely-used technology stack for building full-stack web applications. The MERN stack comprises four main components

➤ MongoDB

A NoSQL database that stores data in a flexible, JSON-like format. It allows for efficient data management and retrieval, making it ideal for handling the dynamic data requirements of a blogging platform..

➤ Express js

A minimalist and flexible Node.js web application framework used to build RESTful APIs. In this project, Express.js handles server-side logic, routing, and middleware for authentication and data processing.

C. React js

A popular front-end library for building user interfaces. It facilitates the creation of dynamic and interactive components, allowing for a seamless user experience. React's component-based architecture also enables efficient state management and rendering.

D. Node js

A JavaScript runtime environment that executes server-side code. Node.js is responsible for handling back-end logic, API requests, and communication with the database, ensuring a robust and scalable application.

By combining these four technologies, the MERN stack allows for end-to-end development using a single programming language—JavaScript—streamlining the development process.

Other Technologies and Libraries

Socket.io powers real-time chat functionality in the platform, allowing bloggers to engage in live conversations through seamless client-server communication. **Tailwind CSS**, a utility-first CSS framework, is utilized for responsive and efficient styling by leveraging pre-defined classes. For secure user authentication and route protection, **JWT (JSON Web Token)** encodes user data, verifying identity on login. State management relies on Redux Toolkit, which streamlines handling complex application states, such as user authentication, blog creation, and chat interactions.

Additionally, the application uses *Express.js middleware* to manage tasks like parsing request bodies, cookie management, and *CORS (Cross-Origin Resource Sharing)* policies, all essential for a robust backend setup. Built on *REST API* principles, the application's web services provide a structured and standardized way to interact with data and functionality, creating a streamlined user experience. This integration of technologies fosters a dynamic, secure, and responsive environment for users to engage in the blogging platform.

III Planning and Development Process

The development of BlogBites took approximately two and half months, divided into the following phases:

- **Planning (2 weeks):** During the initial planning phase, I defined the project scope, identified key features, and created a development roadmap. The requirements for the blog platform were outlined, and a technology stack was selected to achieve the desired functionality.
- **Design (3 weeks):** The design phase involved creating wireframes for the application's user interface, outlining how different components would interact. I used this time to plan the database schema in MongoDB, set up the initial React project structure, and establish a consistent design language using Tailwind CSS.
- **Implementation (6 weeks):** The core development work took place over six weeks, where I implemented the primary features, including user authentication, blog creation, image uploads, and real-time chat using Socket.io. This phase also included the integration of scrolling pagination using TanStack Query for efficiently loading blog posts.
- **Testing and Refinement (1.5 weeks):** The final phase involved testing the application to ensure all features worked as intended. User feedback was incorporated, and bugs were fixed to improve the overall user experience. Stress testing of features like chat and pagination was also performed to ensure the app could handle real-world use cases.

Planning and Development Process

- A) **Authentication and Authorization:** A core component of BlogBites' architecture is its secure authentication and authorization system, essential for user data protection. JSON Web Tokens (JWT) were used for token-based authentication due to their efficiency in securely transmitting user identities between client and server, providing a scalable solution for session management [1]. Upon user login, a JWT is generated and stored as an HTTP-only cookie, safeguarding against client-side attacks, like Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) [2]. Ensuring JWT security included handling token expiration and implementing server-side checks to protect against session hijacking, adhering to security best practices [3].
- B) **Socket.io Implementation:** Real-time communication using Socket.io for the live chat feature presented some challenges, such as managing event listeners and synchronizing chat messages across clients. I tackled these issues by learning the fundamentals of Socket.io and

gradually implementing features like typing indicators and handling message delivery status.

This setup enables real-time communication, allowing users to join chat rooms and receive events associated with those rooms.

```
io.on('connection', (socket) => {
  console.log('A user connected');

  socket.on('joinRoom', (chatRoomId) => {
    socket.join(chatRoomId);
    console.log(`User joined room ${chatRoomId}`);
  });

  socket.on('disconnect', () => {
    console.log('A user disconnected');
  });
});

const PORT = process.env.PORT || 3500;
server.listen(PORT, () => {
  console.log(`Socket server is running on port ${PORT}`);
});
```

C) Scrolling Pagination with React Infinite Scroll

Component: Implementing infinite scrolling pagination for the blog posts required careful handling of data loading and state management. The main challenge was making sure the pagination worked seamlessly when switching between blog categories. I used the *react-infinite-scroll-component* library to manage data fetching and state changes, spending considerable time optimizing the solution to handle category changes while maintaining the current scroll position.

- The *InfiniteScroll* component is used to enable infinite scrolling behavior for the list of blog posts.

```
<InfiniteScroll
  dataLength={bloglist.length}
  next={() => setPage((prevPage) => prevPage +
    1)} hasMore={hasMore}
  loader={ <div style={{ display: 'flex',
    justifyContent: 'center', alignItems: 'center', minHeight:
    200px' }}>
    <CircularProgress />
  </div>}
  endMessage={ <p>No more blogs to
  show</p>}
  />
```

- This prop tells the component how many items are currently displayed (*bloglist.length*). It helps the component

determine when to trigger the `next` function to load more data.

- The `next` function is called when the user scrolls to the bottom. Here, it increments the `page` state by 1, which can then be used to fetch the next set of blog posts. loader specifies what to display while new data is being loaded
- The `hasMore` prop indicates whether there are more items to load. If `true`, it will continue to trigger the `next` function when the user reaches the bottom. If `false`, it will stop further data loading.

IV Features of the Application

➤ User Registration and Authentication:

The application allows users to create an account by registering with their email and password. User authentication is implemented using JSON Web Tokens (JWT), ensuring secure login and access to the application. After registration, users can log in using their credentials and access features such as blog creation and real-time chat. Password management features, including password reset and update, are also integrated to enhance security.

```
const loginUser = tryCatch(async(req,res)>>{
  const {email,password}=req.body

  const userData = await userModel.findOne({ email: email });
  if(!userData){
    return res.status(400).json({message:"user not find",success:false})
  }

  const passwordMatch = await bcrypt.compare(password, userData.password);

  if (!passwordMatch) {
    return res.status(400).json({ message: "Incorrect password", success: false });
  }

  const id = userData.email

  const aboutUser = jwt.sign({id},process.env.secreteKey,{
    expiresIn: '1d'
  })

  res.cookie("userToken", aboutUser, {
    httpOnly: true,
    secure: 'production',
    sameSite: 'None',
    maxAge: 24 * 60 * 60 * 1000
  });

  res.status(200).json({message:"login successfull",success:true})
```

➤ Blog Creation and Management

Users can easily create and manage their blogs on the platform. The blog creation process includes the ability to add a title, write content, upload up to five images, and assign topics related to the blog. Once a blog is published, users can revisit it to make edits or delete it if necessary. The rich text editor allows for easy formatting, making the content more engaging and visually appealing.

➤ Interactivity Features

The platform supports various interactive features that make it a social space for bloggers:

Commenting: Users can comment on blogs to share their thoughts, provide feedback, or engage in discussions.

Liking: Blogs can be liked by other users, providing a way to appreciate content and boost engagement.

Following Users: Users can follow other bloggers, creating a personalized feed of blogs from the people they follow.

Saving Blogs: Blogs can be saved to a user's profile for later reading, allowing them to keep track of content they find interesting or useful.

These features foster a community atmosphere, making the application more than just a blogging platform.

➤ Real-time Chat

The application includes a real-time chat feature powered by Socket.io, enabling users to chat with each other directly within the platform. The chat functionality allows users to engage in one-on-one conversations or group discussions, making it easy to connect and share ideas with other bloggers. Messages are delivered instantly, enhancing the user experience by providing a dynamic and interactive communication tool.

V System Architecture and Design Considerations

The architecture of BlogBites emphasizes scalability and modularity, both crucial for handling potentially high volumes of users and interactions on the platform. MongoDB, as a NoSQL database, supports a flexible schema-less design, which allows for rapid development and scalability as the platform evolves with user needs [1]. The asynchronous nature of Node.js enables efficient handling of concurrent connections, a valuable asset when implementing real-time features like chat using Socket.io [2]. By using RESTful API standards, the platform maintains a decoupled architecture, allowing the front end (React) to communicate seamlessly with the back end (Node.js) via defined endpoints, facilitating future integration with other services or even mobile applications [3].

The use of Tailwind CSS underscores an important trend in web design: rapid prototyping with utility-first CSS frameworks. Tailwind's predefined classes expedite styling without compromising on customization, enabling a consistent and responsive design across various devices [4]. Furthermore, the integration of Redux Toolkit for state management addresses the complexity of managing user-generated data, especially in maintaining the state across user interactions like posts, comments, and chat sessions [5]. This architectural setup not only enhances user experience but also aligns with best practices in modern web development, prioritizing maintainability, flexibility, and performance.

Conclusion

Working on BlogBites helped me grow as a developer by exposing me to various technologies and teaching me how to tackle complex problems. I learned to implement real-time communication using Socket.io, effectively integrating real-time features into web applications. Utilizing the [react-infinite-scroll-component](#), I mastered data fetching, caching, and synchronizing server state with the client for efficient pagination. I also improved my skills in handling asynchronous code with JavaScript's [async/await](#), essential for data fetching and state management. Learning Redux Toolkit refined my ability to manage global state, especially with complex interactions and asynchronous data flows. These experiences enhanced my technical skills, debugging abilities, and feature optimization, making me a more proficient developer.

Backend:-https://github.com/AnanduAppu/blogbites_backend/tree/main

Front-end:-<https://github.com/AnanduAppu/blogbites/tree/main>

Video:-<https://youtu.be/504xB4sFloosi=lPhW35SAPpbkF2It>

REFERENCES

- Tran, D. (2022). *Real-time Communication in Web Applications using Socket.io*. Journal of Interactive Systems, 12(1), 44–56.
- Smith, A., & Jones, T. (2021). *Architectural Patterns for RESTful APIs in Scalable Web Systems*. Computing Technologies Review, 30(5), 220–234.
- Park, H. (2023). *Responsive Design in Modern Web Applications: The Role of Utility-First CSS Frameworks*. Web Development Journal, 20(1), 85–97.
- Brown, L., & Kumar, S. (2023). *State Management in Modern Web Applications: A Study of Redux and its Optimization through Redux Toolkit*. Frontiers in Web Application Development, 8(4), 314–327.
- Wang, Z., et al. (2022). *Authentication Protocols in Web Applications: Ensuring Data Security with JWT and OAuth2*. International Journal of Computer Security, 10(3), 205–212.